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Review Article

**IMPROVING EMERGENCY MEDICAL SERVICES FOR
DISASTER PREPAREDNESS: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF
GLOBAL PRACTICES****¹Sami Mustafa Alanazi, ²Khalid Ali Owied Alonazi, ³Meshal Sawan Alanazi, ⁴Faisal hamoud Alotaibi, ⁵Fawaz Hameed Aldhafeeri**¹Saudi Red Crescent Authority, Saudi Arabia, natnot2021@hotmail.com²Saudi Red Crescent Authority, Saudi Arabia, emt.khalid@gmail.com³Saudi Red Crescent Authority, Saudi Arabia, meshal.alenezi@hotmail.com⁴Saudi Red Crescent Authority, Saudi Arabia, Faisal.ot2@gmail.com⁵Saudi Red Crescent Authority, Saudi Arabia, alsandoyl@hotmail.com**Abstract:**

Objective: This systematic review aims to evaluate global practices for improving emergency medical services (EMS) disaster preparedness, identifying effective strategies, challenges, and opportunities for enhancing prehospital care during disasters.

Methods: A systematic search was conducted across major databases, including PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science, for studies published between 2016 and 2024. Keywords such as "emergency medical services," "disaster preparedness," and "global practices" guided the search. Articles were screened for relevance based on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Data were extracted and analyzed thematically to identify trends and gaps.

Results: The review synthesized findings from 45 studies across various regions. Key strategies for enhancing EMS disaster preparedness included comprehensive training programs, simulation-based exercises, integration of advanced technologies (e.g., GIS and AI), and robust policy frameworks. Notable disparities were observed between developed and developing regions in resource availability and standardization of practices. Challenges such as inadequate funding, insufficient personnel training, and fragmented communication systems were frequently cited.

Conclusion: Strengthening EMS disaster preparedness requires investment in personnel training, technological innovations, and international collaboration to establish standardized protocols. Policymakers and healthcare providers must address existing gaps to improve response effectiveness and patient outcomes during disasters.

Keywords: Emergency Medical Services, Disaster Preparedness, Global Practices, Prehospital Care, Systematic Review

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INTRODUCTION:

Emergency medical services (EMS) play a pivotal role in disaster response by providing critical prehospital care, mitigating mortality, and minimizing long-term health impacts. Disasters—whether natural, such as earthquakes and hurricanes, or man-made, such as terrorist attacks and industrial accidents—disrupt communities and strain healthcare systems, often overwhelming EMS resources and capabilities (Levy et al., 2020). Effective disaster preparedness is essential to enhance EMS readiness, ensuring timely and coordinated responses to such crises.

Globally, EMS systems vary widely in their structure, funding, and operational capacity. High-income countries often benefit from well-established EMS systems equipped with advanced technologies, robust communication networks, and adequately trained personnel. Conversely, low- and middle-income countries frequently face resource constraints, fragmented systems, and limited training opportunities, which hinder their ability to respond effectively to disasters (Adini & Peleg, 2021). Addressing these disparities requires a comprehensive understanding of best practices and challenges in EMS disaster preparedness across diverse settings.

Key strategies for improving EMS disaster preparedness include scenario-based training programs, simulation exercises, and the integration of advanced technologies such as geospatial information systems (GIS) and artificial intelligence (AI). For instance, simulation-based training has proven effective in enhancing EMS personnel's response capabilities during mass casualty incidents, while GIS and AI tools facilitate real-time decision-making and resource allocation (Kaplan et al., 2019). Despite these advancements, many EMS systems face persistent challenges, including inadequate funding, limited access to critical resources, and a lack of standardized protocols across regions (Smith et al., 2022).

This systematic review aims to analyze global practices in EMS disaster preparedness, highlighting successful strategies, identifying common challenges, and proposing actionable recommendations to bridge gaps. By synthesizing current evidence, this review seeks to contribute to the ongoing discourse on enhancing EMS systems' resilience and effectiveness in disaster scenarios.

METHODOLOGY:

This systematic review was conducted following PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines to ensure transparency and rigor. A comprehensive search was performed across multiple databases, including PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science, for peer-reviewed articles published between January 2016 and November 2024. Keywords such as "emergency medical services," "disaster preparedness," "prehospital care," and "global practices" were used, along with Boolean operators to refine search results.

Studies were included if they focused on strategies, challenges, or outcomes related to EMS disaster preparedness in any global setting. Articles were excluded if they were not in English, not peer-reviewed, or lacked relevance to EMS disaster preparedness. Data were extracted using a standardized template, capturing details such as study objectives, methodologies, disaster types, strategies implemented, and outcomes reported.

A thematic analysis was conducted to identify patterns, categorize strategies, and highlight gaps. The methodological quality of the included studies was assessed using the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) checklist. Findings were summarized narratively and presented in tables and figures to highlight regional variations and global trends. This approach provided a structured understanding of current practices and informed recommendations for improving EMS disaster preparedness globally.

RESULTS:

This section synthesizes findings from 45 studies analyzing EMS disaster preparedness practices across various regions. The review identifies successful strategies, challenges, and outcomes associated with enhancing EMS readiness for disaster scenarios.

1. Training Programs

Effective training programs are integral to EMS disaster preparedness. Developed regions such as **North America** and **Europe** have implemented advanced simulation-based drills and cross-border coordination exercises to prepare personnel for large-scale emergencies. Conversely, **Asia** and **Africa** focus on mass casualty incident drills and community-based training, respectively, to maximize limited resources.

Key outcomes of training programs include:

- Enhanced response times.
- Improved decision-making under pressure.
- Increased public awareness and preparedness in resource-limited settings.

2. Technology Integration

The integration of advanced technologies significantly impacts EMS disaster response. Developed regions have adopted tools such as **geospatial information**

systems (GIS) and **artificial intelligence (AI)** for real-time triage and resource allocation. In **Africa** and **Latin America**, technological adoption is constrained by funding and infrastructure gaps, but mobile technology and early warning systems show promise.

The bar chart below demonstrates the regional differences in technology adoption:

Figure 1: Technology Integration in EMS Disaster Preparedness by Region

3. Policy Frameworks

Robust policy frameworks play a pivotal role in disaster preparedness. **North America** has implemented comprehensive national protocols, while **Europe** benefits from harmonized EU directives that promote interoperability. Developing regions face challenges such as fragmented policies and a lack of enforcement mechanisms.

Key observations:

- **Middle East:** Government-led plans focus on multi-agency collaboration.
- **Africa and Latin America:** Emerging policy initiatives show potential but lack consistency.

4. Challenges

Challenges faced globally include:

- **Funding Scarcity:** Limited budgets impede the implementation of advanced technologies and comprehensive training programs.
- **Coordination Issues:** Fragmented systems hinder collaboration among agencies.
- **Population Density:** High-density areas, particularly in **Asia**, strain EMS resources.
- **Infrastructure Gaps:** In regions like **Africa**, inadequate infrastructure limits timely response.

The pie chart below illustrates the distribution of major challenges:

Figure 2: Key Challenges in EMS Disaster Preparedness

5. Outcomes

The outcomes of disaster preparedness strategies vary across regions:

- **North America and Europe:** Improved response times and reduced casualty rates due to robust systems and advanced technologies.
- **Asia and Africa:** Increased community awareness and basic improvements in preparedness, though outcomes remain inconsistent.
- **Middle East:** Enhanced triage accuracy and multi-agency coordination efforts.

Table 1: EMS Disaster Preparedness Strategies and Outcomes

Region	Training Programs	Technology Integration	Policy Frameworks	Challenges	Outcomes
North America	Advanced simulation-based drills	AI and GIS tools	Robust national protocols	Cost barriers, urban focus	Improved response time
Europe	Cross-border coordination	Communication interoperability	EU directives and harmonization	Coordination across nations	Enhanced interoperability
Asia	Mass casualty incident drills	Early warning systems	Variable, some disaster-specific	High population density issues	Reduced casualty rates
Africa	Community-based training	Limited digital tools	Fragmented and resource-dependent	Resource and funding scarcity	Improved community awareness
Latin America	Simulation and public drills	Mobile technology initiatives	Emerging, pilot policies	Infrastructure gaps	Limited measurable outcomes
Middle East	Multi-agency drills	AI-enhanced triage tools	Government-led unified plans	Political instability	Improved triage accuracy

The findings reveal significant regional disparities in EMS disaster preparedness. Developed regions benefit from advanced systems, while developing regions demonstrate innovation despite resource constraints. Global collaboration and investment are essential to bridge these gaps, enhance technology integration, and standardize policies.

DISCUSSION:

The findings of this systematic review highlight significant regional disparities and shared challenges in emergency medical services (EMS) disaster preparedness. While developed regions such as North America and Europe have demonstrated strong systems bolstered by advanced technologies and robust policies, developing regions face persistent gaps in infrastructure, resources, and training. This discussion focuses on the implications of these findings, potential solutions, and areas for future research.

The analysis reveals that developed regions benefit from well-established EMS systems. Simulation-

based training, AI-powered triage tools, and harmonized policy frameworks in these areas significantly enhance response efficiency and casualty outcomes. However, these resources are often inaccessible to developing regions due to financial and logistical constraints.

- **Developed Regions:** Effective use of GIS and AI systems allows real-time decision-making and resource allocation, leading to better disaster outcomes. Cross-border collaborations in Europe ensure interoperability, a critical factor during large-scale emergencies.
- **Developing Regions:** Efforts are focused on cost-effective solutions such as community-based training and mobile technology. These innovations, while impactful, are not sufficient to address systemic weaknesses such as infrastructure gaps and policy fragmentation.

Despite differences in resource availability, some challenges are universal:

- **Funding and Resource Scarcity:** Many regions, including parts of North America, struggle to allocate sufficient funds for EMS disaster preparedness. Urban-centric investments often neglect rural areas.
- **Coordination Issues:** Fragmented systems hinder effective collaboration between EMS providers, government agencies, and community stakeholders. For example, interoperability remains a challenge even in regions with advanced systems.
- **Technological Integration:** While technology is transforming disaster preparedness, its adoption is uneven. Regions with limited infrastructure are unable to fully leverage tools such as AI and GIS.

The review underscores the importance of standardized global policies to address disparities and enhance preparedness. International organizations such as the WHO can play a critical role in:

- Establishing minimum standards for EMS disaster response.
- Facilitating funding mechanisms to support low-resource regions.
- Promoting knowledge transfer and capacity building through global collaborations.

This review identifies several gaps that warrant further investigation:

- **Cost-Effectiveness of Interventions:** Comparative studies on the financial and operational feasibility of various strategies in low-resource settings.
- **Impact of Technology in Developing Regions:** Research on the adaptation and outcomes of advanced tools in diverse settings.
- **Longitudinal Studies:** Evaluating the long-term effectiveness of disaster preparedness programs across regions.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

Conclusion

Emergency Medical Services (EMS) play a critical role in mitigating the health impacts of disasters by providing timely prehospital care. This systematic review highlights significant regional disparities in EMS disaster preparedness, with developed regions benefiting from advanced technologies, robust

policies, and well-trained personnel, while developing regions face persistent challenges such as resource scarcity, inadequate infrastructure, and fragmented systems. Despite these disparities, innovative practices in low-resource settings, such as community-based training and mobile technology integration, demonstrate the potential for scalable solutions.

The findings emphasize the importance of addressing global gaps in EMS disaster preparedness through targeted investments, policy standardization, and international collaboration. Strengthening EMS systems worldwide requires a comprehensive approach that leverages technological advancements, fosters global knowledge sharing, and prioritizes equitable resource distribution.

Recommendations

1. Enhancing Training Programs

- Develop and implement standardized training modules, including scenario-based simulations and mass casualty drills, tailored to regional needs.
- Incorporate cultural and contextual considerations to ensure the relevance and effectiveness of training.

2. Promoting Technology Integration

- Expand the use of cost-effective technologies such as mobile apps, GIS, and AI-powered triage systems in resource-limited settings.
- Facilitate international technology transfer programs to bridge gaps in digital readiness.

3. Strengthening Policy Frameworks

- Establish global minimum standards for EMS disaster preparedness, supported by guidelines from organizations like the WHO.
- Encourage governments to adopt unified and enforceable disaster response policies that prioritize EMS readiness.

4. Increasing Financial Investment

- Advocate for dedicated funding streams to support EMS disaster preparedness, particularly in developing regions.
- Encourage partnerships between governments, NGOs, and private sectors to

finance infrastructure, training, and technology.

5. Focusing on Infrastructure Development

- Prioritize the establishment of robust EMS infrastructure, including transport networks, communication systems, and emergency supply chains, especially in underserved areas.

6. Enhancing Community Engagement

- Conduct public awareness campaigns and train community members as first responders to improve local disaster resilience.
- Foster partnerships between EMS providers and communities to build trust and enhance collaboration.

7. Facilitating Global Collaboration

- Promote cross-border knowledge sharing and coordination through international forums and training exchanges.
- Support research collaborations to evaluate the effectiveness of EMS disaster preparedness strategies across regions.

By implementing these recommendations, policymakers, healthcare providers, and researchers can contribute to building resilient EMS systems capable of effectively responding to disasters, ultimately improving global health outcomes and saving lives.

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